

All Databases Search

National Center for Biotechnology Information

COVID-19 Information

[Public health information \(CDC\)](#) |
 [Research information \(NIH\)](#) |
 [SARS-CoV-2 data \(NCBI\)](#) |
 [Prevention and treatment information \(HHS\)](#) |
 [Español](#)

UNITE
 A new NIH initiative to end structural racism and achieve racial equity in the biomedical research enterprise.

[LEARN MORE](#)

- NCBI Home**
- Resource List (A-Z)
- All Resources
- Chemicals & Bioassays
- Data & Software
- DNA & RNA
- Domains & Structures
- Genes & Expression
- Genetics & Medicine
- Genomes & Maps
- Homology
- Literature

Welcome to NCBI

The National Center for Biotechnology Information advances science and health by providing access to biomedical and genomic information.

[About the NCBI](#) |
 [Mission](#) |
 [Organization](#) |
 [NCBI News & Blog](#)

<p>Submit</p> <p>Deposit data or manuscripts into NCBI databases</p>		
---	---	--

- Popular Resources**
- PubMed
 - Bookshelf
 - PubMed Central
 - BLAST
 - Nucleotide
 - Genome
 - SNP
 - Gene
 - Protein
 - PubChem

COVID-19 Information

[Public health information \(CDC\)](#) | [Research information \(NIH\)](#) | [SARS-CoV-2 data \(NCBI\)](#) | [Prevention and treatment information \(HHS\)](#) | [Español](#)

Learn

NCBI creates a variety of educational products including courses, workshops, webinars, training materials and documentation. NCBI educational events are free and open to everyone. All NCBI educational materials are available for anyone to re-use and distribute.

Follow Us

NCBI News & Blog

A more modern PMC is on its way – there's still time to give us feedback!

08 Nov 2021

In June, we announced the arrival of PMC Labs, where you can test drive the work underway to create a more modern PMC website. Since then, we've continued to talk to users, gather input,

Webinars & Courses

In-person courses, live webinars and webinar recordings

Conferences & Presentations

Booth exhibits and workshops at scientific conferences

Tutorials

Tutorials: Training materials in HTML, PDF and video formats

Documentation

Online manuals, handbooks, fact sheets and FAQs

News, Blog & Social Media

Keep up with the latest NCBI news and follow NCBI on social media sites, including FaceBook, Twitter, Google+, LinkedIn and the NCBI Insights blog.

NCBI News & Blog

A more modern PMC is on its way – there's still time to give us feedback!

08 Nov 2021

In June, we announced the arrival of PMC Labs, where you can test drive the work underway to create a more modern PMC website. Since then, we've continued to talk to users, gather input,

NCBI's Genome Data viewer now displays both NCBI RefSeq and submitted assemblies

07 Nov 2021

NCBI's Genome Data Viewer (GDV) now supports visualization and analysis of nearly 400 submitter-annotated chromosome-level assemblies from the INSDC

Three outdated browsers (1000 Genomes, dbGaP Data, and Get-RM) to retire in April 2022. Data available in GDV

28 Oct 2021

The Genome Data Viewer (GDV) is now the comprehensive NCBI genome browser. The development of GDV led to a few different types

[More...](#)

COVID-19 Information

[Public health information \(CDC\)](#) | [Research information \(NIH\)](#) | [SARS-CoV-2 data \(NCBI\)](#) | [Prevention and treatment information \(HHS\)](#) | [Español](#)

Please visit the [NCBI Outreach Events](#) page to access the current offerings of NCBI Webinars, Workshops and Codeathons.

NCBI Outreach Events Past Webinars

Filter this table

Date	Day & Time	Title & Description	Location	Materials
Nov 3, 2021	Wed, 12:00-12:45pm	dbGaP submission improvements and GaPTools In this webinar, you will learn about data submission and processing improvements to dbGaP, NIH's database of Genotype and Phenotype individual-level data associated with human research studies. You will see how we have made submission easier through the Submission Portal using automated preliminary validation and how you can use GaPTools, a stand-alone data validation tool, on your own submission to expedite the submission process. Join us to discover how dbGaP ensures integrity and high-quality in the genomic data that scientists can access to further their research.	Online webinar	Materials Recording
Oct 20, 2021	Wed, 12:00-12:45pm	Introducing the updated PubMed E-utilities (API) NCBI will launch an updated version of the E-utilities API for PubMed on April 4, 2022. With few exceptions, this change will not affect the E-utility URLs you currently use but will bring the search results up to date with the web version of PubMed released in 2020 and improve reliability. Attend this webinar to learn about how these changes will affect your	Online webinar	Materials Recording

Index of /pub/education/public_webinars/2021/11Nov03_GaPTools

Name	Last modified	Size
Parent Directory		-
GapTools_demo.mp4	2021-11-03 11:26	56M
dbGaP_Submissions_GapTools.pptx	2021-11-03 11:26	2.9M
dbGaP_Submissions_GapTools.slides.pdf	2021-11-03 11:26	1.7M

Webinars & Courses

In-person courses, live webinars and webinar recordings

Conferences & Presentations

Booth exhibits and workshops at scientific conferences

Tutorials

Tutorials: Training materials in HTML, PDF and video formats

Documentation

Online manuals, handbooks, fact sheets and FAQs

News, Blog & Social Media

Keep up with the latest NCBI news and follow NCBI on social media sites, including FaceBook, Twitter, Google+, LinkedIn and the NCBI Insights blog.

NCBI News & Blog

A more modern PMC is on its way – there's still time to give us feedback!

08 Nov 2021

In June, we announced the arrival of PMC Labs, where you can test drive the work underway to create a more modern PMC website. Since then, we've continued to talk to users, gather input,

NCBI's Genome Data viewer now displays both NCBI RefSeq and submitted assemblies

07 Nov 2021

NCBI's Genome Data Viewer (GDV) now supports visualization and analysis of nearly 400 submitter-annotated chromosome-level assemblies from the INSDC

Three outdated browsers (1000 Genomes, dbGaP Data, and Get-RM) to retire in April 2022. Data available in GDV

28 Oct 2021

The Genome Data Viewer (GDV) is now the comprehensive NCBI genome browser. The development of GDV led to a few different types

[More...](#)

COVID-19 Information
[Public health information \(CDC\)](#) | [Research information \(NIH\)](#) | [SARS-CoV-2 data \(NCBI\)](#) | [Prevention and treatment information \(HHS\)](#) | [Español](#)

Conferences & Presentations

Booth exhibits, workshops, presentations and posters at scientific conferences.
 The time displayed for each event is based on the time zone for the conference location.

Plant and Animal Genome XXVIII Conference			
Jan 11-15, 2020	Sat-Wed	NCBI staff will participate in the The Plant and Animal Genome XXVIII Conference in San Diego. Attend NCBI presentations, posters and visit us at the NCBI Booth to learn about NCBI research and products.	Town and Country Hotel San Diego, CA
	Sun, 3:00pm-8:30pm	NCBI Exhibit Booth — — Learn how to use NCBI resources for plant and animals genomes. Give feedback to help shape NCBI resources to best fit your needs. Come and meet with NCBI staff.	Booth #321
	Mon, 9:30am-5pm		
	Tue, 9:30am-3:00pm		
	Mon, 12:50pm-3:00pm	NCBI Genome Resources NCBI Wants Your Sequence Data! How Do I Get It There? Annotation of Eukaryote Genomes at NCBI Accessing Homologous Gene Datasets at NCBI The New PubMed is Here! Taxonomy Lookup and Data Retrieval: How to Find and Stream Genomic Data in the Cloud!	Workshop Pacific Salon 1

Webinars & Courses

In-person courses, live webinars and webinar recordings

Conferences & Presentations

Booth exhibits and workshops at scientific conferences

Tutorials

Tutorials: Training materials in HTML, PDF and video formats

Documentation

Online manuals, handbooks, fact sheets and FAQs

News, Blog & Social Media

Keep up with the latest NCBI news and follow NCBI on social media sites, including FaceBook, Twitter, Google+, LinkedIn and the NCBI Insights blog.

NCBI News & Blog

A more modern PMC is on its way – there's still time to give us feedback!

08 Nov 2021

In June, we announced the arrival of PMC Labs, where you can test drive the work underway to create a more modern PMC website. Since then, we've continued to talk to users, gather input,

NCBI's Genome Data viewer now displays both NCBI RefSeq and submitted assemblies

07 Nov 2021

NCBI's Genome Data Viewer (GDV) now supports visualization and analysis of nearly 400 submitter-annotated chromosome-level assemblies from the INSDC

Three outdated browsers (1000 Genomes, dbGaP Data, and Get-RM) to retire in April 2022. Data available in GDV

28 Oct 2021

The Genome Data Viewer (GDV) is now the comprehensive NCBI genome browser. The development of GDV led to a few different types

[More...](#)

Tutorials

Training materials in HTML, PDF and Video formats

Filter this table

Type	Title and Description
Video	A Guide to NCBI: Gene Expression, Part 1 Part 1 of the gene expression module from "A Librarian's Guide to NCBI," a workshop held at the National Library of Medicine in April 2013
Video	A Guide to NCBI: Gene Expression, Part 2 Part 2 of the gene expression module from "A Librarian's Guide to NCBI," a workshop held at the National Library of Medicine in April 2013
Video	A Guide to NCBI: Gene Expression, Part 3 Part 3 of the gene expression module from "A Librarian's Guide to NCBI," a workshop held at the National Library of Medicine in April 2013
PDF	Align 2 Sequences Aligning two groups of sequences and displaying the results in the NCBI sequence viewer
Video	Assign Downloaders for dbGaP Data Learn how an authorized user of controlled-access data can assign a downloader role to someone in his/her institution
PDF	Batch Data Download and Programmatic Access Survey of methods for accessing NCBI data using FTP, Aspera and APIs
PDF	BLAST Guide Overview of the various NCBI BLAST services and reports
Video	BLAST Results: Expect values, part 1

Webinars & Courses

In-person courses, live webinars and webinar recordings

Conferences & Presentations

Booth exhibits and workshops at scientific conferences

Tutorials

Tutorials: Training materials in HTML, PDF and video formats

Documentation

Online manuals, handbooks, fact sheets and FAQs

News, Blog & Social Media

Keep up with the latest NCBI news and follow NCBI on social media sites, including FaceBook, Twitter, Google+, LinkedIn and the NCBI Insights blog.

NCBI News & Blog

A more modern PMC is on its way – there's still time to give us feedback!

08 Nov 2021

In June, we announced the arrival of PMC Labs, where you can test drive the work underway to create a more modern PMC website. Since then, we've continued to talk to users, gather input,

NCBI's Genome Data viewer now displays both NCBI RefSeq and submitted assemblies

07 Nov 2021

NCBI's Genome Data Viewer (GDV) now supports visualization and analysis of nearly 400 submitter-annotated chromosome-level assemblies from the INSDC

Three outdated browsers (1000 Genomes, dbGaP Data, and Get-REM) to retire in April 2022. Data available in GDV

28 Oct 2021

The Genome Data Viewer (GDV) is now the comprehensive NCBI genome browser. The development of GDV led to a few different types

[More...](#)

All Databases ▾

Search NCBI

Search

[Public health information \(CDC\)](#) |
 [Research information \(NIH\)](#) |
 [SARS-CoV-2 data \(NCBI\)](#) |
 [Prevention and treatment information \(HHS\)](#) |
 [Español](#)

Documentation

Online manuals, handbooks, fact sheets and FAQs

Filter this table

Resource	Description	Materials
1000 Genomes browser	genome viewer for 1000 Genomes Project data	help FAQ factsheet
Assembly	information and sequences for assembled genomes	help download FAQ factsheet
BankIt	online nucleotide sequence submission service	help
BioProject	catalog of high-throughput genome-wide studies	help factsheet
BioSample	sample repository for the BioProject database	help FAQ
BioSystems	pathways with links to genes, proteins and chemicals	help FAQ citation
BLAST (standalone version)	downloadable version of the sequence similarity search tool	help FAQ factsheet
BLAST (web version)	online version of the sequence similarity search tool	help FAQ factsheet
BLAST (cloud version)	cloud-based version of the sequence similarity search tool	help FAQ
Bookshelf	catalog of books and documents	help FAQ factsheet

گروه ۱۳

ارائه کلاس بیوانفورماتیک

اعضا: حامد افقری - زهرا رضایی - رضا شفیعی

THE END